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Quantification of Local Cooling Impacted by Urban Green Spaces: Insights from Cyclone Amphan

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Abstract: Due to the urban heat island (UHI) effect, rapid unplanned urbanization has caused the green cover of Indian cities to deteriorate and raised urban temperatures. Understanding the function of urban green spaces (UGS) in reducing the UHI is crucial given that the population of the Indian urban areas is projected to be 800 million people by 2050. To measure the cooling benefits supplied by UGS beyond their bounds, high-resolution Landsat data and data from Google Earth are combined with spatial statistical analysis in this study. The cooling effect is analyzed for the famous botanical garden of age-old 'Acharya Jagadish Chandra Bose Indian Botanic Garden' in Howrah, India. The result showed a temperature variance of 1.23°C (R² coefficients of 0.78) till the distance of 400 m beyond the park boundary. This study is set out to explore the changes that took place in the local microclimate of the region near the garden after the super cyclone 'Amphan', that struck the city between 16th to 21st May 2020 leading to the uprooting of several trees and other damages to city's infrastructure. The quantification of the local cooling resulted in the increased value of temperature variance to 3.08°C influencing a gradient of 300 m from the periphery of the park in post cyclonic events. The study thus brings into light the impact of the urban green that has a significant cooling impact on its neighborhoods and the preservation of such large green spaces is appreciated that would lead to sustainable urban environmental management. The Smart City mission that has talked very less in the domain of urban greening can address the particular study which shows the immense contribution of urban greens in regulating the localized surface temperature.

Keywords: Urban heat island, Urban green spaces, Local cooling effects

Introduction

Often, a large urban park or a woodland near a dense settlement act as a place of refreshment. LST of a place affects the microclimate of the place, which in the other way is affected by the urban park size and complexity on PCI intensity. A park benefits its surrounding generating natural cooling effect, which increases with increase in the size of the park (Lin et al., 2015). It is observed that the woodland effects a lot more than a simple grassland in lowering the LST. The change in LULC Cameron Highlands from 2009 to 2019 has significantly affected the LST of the place. An increase of 2–30°C with a decrease of 8.88% of

forest cover is observed in ten years period (How Jin Aik et al., 2020).

'Amphan' has caused a priceless damage to the treasure house of 13,000 trees of about 1,100 species, the 'Acharya Jagadish Chandra Bose Indian Botanic Garden'. 1000 trees fell down some of which were of large foliage with trunk girth of more than a meter ageing more than a century (Singh, 2020). The 'Great Banyan tree' could withstand the drastic lashings of Amphan as only 10% of the prop roots on the western edge got damaged (Cyclone Amphan: Storm Strikes 270-year-old Great Banyan Tree - Telegraph India, n.d.).

The present study tries to establish the fact that, the garden is responsible for creating a microclimate in its surroundings. It also establishes an analysis of the dynamics of microclimate change due to cyclone 'Amphan'. The analysis is carried out from 2015 to 2021 by correlating the relation between the parameters of NDVI and LST.

Data and methods

This focuses on a botanical garden in the Indian city of Howrah, which spans 270 acres and is spreading on the west bank of the river Hooghly. The garden is home to thousands of different varieties of domestic and exotic tree species. It has been granted permission by the Indian Botanical Survey. The garden is encircled by the Ganges River in the south, the IEST Shibpur campus in the southeast, and dense habitation in the north, northeast, and west. With an elevation of 12 meters, Kolkata has a tropical wet and dry climate (Aw).

Landsat images were collected from the United States Geological Survey website for the five years from 2015 to 2020. Landsat imagery of 30 m resolution was chosen among other satellite imagery because it is easily available and has historical coverage in a long span.

Data are collected twice each year deriving from the first and last quarter of the year. These dates were selected to retain a constant seasonal effect, thus biases will be reduced, which is necessary for any change detection analysis. The images used were taken for zero cloud coverage. Data collected for the first quarter of the years of 2018 is from Landsat 8.

Methodology

Deriving park cooling intensity

The park cooling intensity is described by Lin et al. that is generated by the difference of the temperature between the inside (T_p) and outside (T_u) of the garden which can be LST or air temperature. According to the curve line method the graph showing PCI increases with the increase in the distance from the vegetated area of significant size and gradually decreased or gets constant. This phenomenon is useful for obtaining the change in LST influencing the microclimate of the park. The paper adopts the method of Park cooling intensity (PCI) calculation to derive the cooling extent of the park.

Figure 1 Research framework

Deriving land surface temperature

The split window algorithm (SWA) is applied to extract LST from the Landsat 8 using both bands 10 and 11 (Wang et al., 2019). The SWA takes advantage of the differential atmospheric absorption in two adjacent TIR channels to retrieve LST (McMillin, 1975). The digital number is converted to the top of the atmosphere's spectral radiance. The spectral radiance of the thermal bands has to be converted to brightness temperature (BT) after the conversion of the digital numbers to reflectance. The result obtained must be converted to Celsius, hence 273.15 is subtracted.

Deriving Normalised Difference Vegetation Index

Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) is calculated using the bands of red and near-infrared band of the Landsat.

$$NDVI = \left(\frac{NIR - Red}{NIR + Red} \right)$$

NIR = Near-infrared band; Red = Red band.

Landsat 8 data used Bands 5 (infrared) and 4 (red), whereas Landsat 7 used Bands 4 and 3, to calculate the NDVI values.

Results and Discussion

The study selects the Landsat 8 image of the year 2015, to 2021, for analysing the Land surface temperature of the site. PCI recorded from the site is derived from the LST maps generated using the Split window algorithm. The extent of cooling intensity of the garden is assessed by the method of PCI calculation. The temperature inside the selected site is obtained by clearly denoting the park boundaries were determined based on high-resolution Google Earth images. Past research has shown the cooling effect of the urban park can influence up to 100 m to 800 m of regional setting from the periphery of the park. The study aided the spatial demarcation of buffer zones at an interval of 100 m up to 600 m. The river Ganga flows along the south of the site, hence the study is limited to the north, east, and west of the site having a dense urban fabric. The buffer zones were used as a basis to investigate the temperature outside the garden that would be necessary to compute the PCI. PCI is generated applying the fishnet tool of Arcgis retrieving the LST data followed by subsequent calculations.

Analysing PCI at pre cyclonic events:

The analysis resulted in 20.97°C as the mean LST inside the park (Tp) and the temperature (Tu) of 21.683, 21.998, 22.043, 22.1885, 22.1965, 22.19 for the buffers of 100 m,

200 m, 300 m, 400 m, 500 m, and 600 m respectively. A sharp rise in PCI is seen for the 100 m buffer zone, whereas a gradual rise continued till the interval of 400 m from the garden boundary. The calculated PCI for the far distances is seen to present a constant trend line without undergoing significant change. The relation between PCI and buffer distance of the park has R2 coefficient of 0.78 for the distance of 400 m which can be considered as the zone of influence. The PCI intensity is calculated to be 1.23°C and the PCI centre is seen in the garden itself.

Analysing PCI at post-cyclonic events

The Amphan is thus believed to pose a change in the radius of influence of PCI of the garden. The satellite image of Landsat 8 is studied, having acquiring date of 16.11.20 to see the relationship of PCI and the distance from park boundary (L). Sampling toolset component in 'Arcmap' software is used to create fishnet over the selected area that includes the site and its surroundings up to a buffer of 600 m to generate random points. A fishnet containing 60 rows and 60 columns are created containing 3600 sample points for data collection, from which the area of interest is intersected to generate necessary sample points for data collection.

The relation between PCI and the distance from park boundary (L) in meter after the occurrence of Amphan. The changes in PCI and also the distance of influence are clearly seen to rise and lessened respectively. Here the cooling influence of the garden seems to exist till the distance of 300 m from the boundary of the garden, which is less than a 100 m if compared with pre-Amphan situation. The cooling intensity has also changed its dynamics as the PCI obtained at 300 m distance is 3.09, which is higher than PCI calculated before Amphan.

Comparative analysis

Table 1 represents a comparative study of NDVI verses LST of the park itself taking into account the pre and post cyclonic event. The test results are taken obtaining from the selected time of the year to denote significant change. Table 1 shows the data processing result of NDVI and LST of the site. The mean NDVI calculated for 2019 is 0.29, for March 2020 it is 0.23, for November 2020 it is 0.18, for 2021 it is 0.19. The mean LST is 22.33°C for 2019, 28.31°C for March 2020, 25.48°C for November 2020, 30.12°C for 2021. All these data show the result of the first quarter of the year. In Table 1, NDVI and LST results are shown for the first and last quarters of the year.

Table 1 NDVI and LST of the first and last

Year	March (1 st quarter of the year)		AMPHAN	November (4 th quarter of the year)	
	mean NDVI	mean LST (°C)		mean NDVI	mean LST (°C)
2019				0.29	22.33
2020	0.23	28.31		0.18	25.48
2021	0.19	30.12			

Conclusion

The present study that revolves around the cooling effect of the urban parks explores the area of the botanical garden located in a dense urban settlement of the city Howrah, second largest city of India. This study shows that the garden is capable of creating a PCI effect on its surroundings thus influencing the local microclimate which can prevent the formation of UHI. The cooling effect intensity increases as distance from the park boundary increases and gradually comes to a constant value with further distance. The temperature difference between the interior of the park and the zones 400 m from the park boundary is 1.23°C in pre Amphan situation which seemed to increase to 3.08°C and radius of PCI influence became 300 m in the post Amphan situation.

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